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INTERNATIONAL SAFEGUARDS
FOR CHILDREN IN SPORT

**GOOD PRACTICE IN
BUILDING A KNOWLEDGE
AND LEARNING
COMMUNITY:
THE INTERNATIONAL
SAFEGUARDS FOR
CHILDREN IN SPORT**

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2024

Introduction

The International Safeguards for Children in Sport is a global initiative with more than 150 members spanning six continents. The initiative firmly believes that it is every child's right to be safe during sport and is determined to end abuse in sporting contexts declaring 'all children, everywhere, safe in sport'. To support this goal, the International Safeguards for Children in Sport Initiative produces [tools and provides guidance](#) building on the eight core pillars of good practice known as the [International Safeguards for Children in Sport](#) (the International Safeguards), as well as encouraging action, in particular through the annual celebration of Safe Sport Day on August 8th.

The 8 Safeguards:

- 01** —Developing your policy
- 02** —Procedures for responding to safeguarding concerns
- 03** —Advice and support
- 04** — Minimising risks to children
- 05** —Guidelines for behaviour
- 06** —Recruiting, training and communicating
- 07** —Working with partners
- 08** —Monitoring and evaluating

The initiative is governed by an Advisory Board consisting of sport, sport for development, Government, and child protection organisations. The Board is supported by an International Working Group, that promotes safeguarding and creates resources and opportunities for learning and sharing good practice.

Background

The International Safeguards for Children in Sport initiative was first established in 2012, when an international group of sport and sport for development organisations came together to discuss safeguarding in sport and the need for action. There were two key founding members of this group: the [UK's Child Protection in Sport Unit](#), who, at the time, was the only organisation globally that was dedicated to child protection specifically in the context of sport, and [Keeping Children Safe](#), an international organisation promoting safeguarding in a range of contexts and countries in the international development sphere.

By drawing together the insights and learning of these two organisations, the initial Founder Organisations were able to draft the first iteration of the International Safeguards for Children in Sport – with 13 'standards' related to safe sport practice. The group then embarked on a two-year pilot, including testing and refinement with an international group of 53 'pioneer' organisations, arranged into learning sets. Each learning set met virtually around 6 times per year, supported by one of the Founder Organisations, to discuss their progress implementing the 13 standards, any issues they faced, and any recommendations they had.

At the end of the pilot process, a team of independent researchers were commissioned to explore the impact of the International Safeguards for Children in Sport on organisational practice, and to make recommendations about the final parameters of the 13 Standards related to safe sport practice.

In 2014, using the learning and insights from the global team of 12 pioneer organisations, [eight International Safeguards](#) were launched, followed by companion Implementation Guides in 2016. In 2017, the International Safeguards were translated into 12 languages and in 2020, the initiative began marking 08/08 as Safe Sport Day.

Throughout this time, the initiative has been supported by a group comprised of NGOs, Humanitarian, Networks, Sport, Child Rights, and Academic institutions, who have provided expertise and services freely to create the Implementation Guides, conduct research on progress in implementation of safeguards, create social media campaigns, and running mentoring pilots.

The structure to support the International Safeguards for Children in Sport initiative has evolved over that time as well:

- 2012-2016: A group of Founder Organisations acted as both governance for the initiative and the Working Group, supporting a global group of pioneer organisations to pilot the International Safeguards, arranged in international learning sets.
- 2017 – 2019: The learning sets were disbanded, and the pioneers, founders and other interested parties were invited to join a new Advisory Board, or one of three Working Groups aligned with the new strategy, focused on: implementation; advocacy & communication; and quality assurance.
- 2020 – date: The three Working Groups were collapsed into a single Working Group of engaged members, who are responsible for delivering the annual plan. The Advisory Board continues to provide strategic direction and overall governance for the initiative.

The International Safeguards for Children in Sport initiative continues its work as a collective united by the mission:

- To support and influence organisations and Governments responsible for the policy environment, to improve safeguarding in sport, and;
- To support and influence organisations at the start of their safeguarding journey, involved in the delivery of sport, to develop their policies and practice to make sport safer for children.

International Safeguards for Children in Sport initiative’s activities fall under two broad objectives:

- To share, and support organisations to share, relevant knowledge, with a focus on those starting out on their safeguarding journey.
- To raise awareness of safeguarding and the International Safeguards in our target audiences and influence them to take action.

To date the International Safeguards for Children in Sport initiative has been coordinated by UNICEF UK, but future plans involve appointing a new organisation to act as a ‘Backbone’ for the initiative – managing staff, resources, fundraising and coordination on behalf of the Advisory Board and Working Group.

Reflection and Learning

COLLECTIVE OWNERSHIP

All the Founder Organisations, and the members of Working Groups and the Advisory Board that have followed over time, have a sense of shared ownership of the initiative. Decisions are taken collaboratively and with a wide range of input.

There has been consistency in some core members, notably the initiative chair and coordinator, and this has helped with continuity and clarity - but new members joining has helped with new ideas and ongoing momentum. The level of commitment and shared ownership by these engaged organisations has been key to the initiative’s success to date.

COORDINATION

A single organisation coordinates the initiative, the Advisory Board and Working Group, and all the key projects. Meetings, held quarterly, are set at the start of the year, and all Advisory Board and Working Group members are clear on their roles and responsibilities. This means everything is aligned and consistent.

That said, the coordinator function is a 'single point of failure' for the whole initiative. If the current role holder was no longer able to take this on, and a suitable alternative provider of this free capacity for the initiative wasn't identified, the initiative would struggle to continue in its current form.

MEMBERSHIP

Members join the initiative by [taking a pledge](#). This is a relatively low bar for entry, and means any organisation that commits to improving safeguarding, and who also produces a basic safeguarding policy, can be recognised as a member.

This approach comes with a significant risk. If an individual member engages in activity that doesn't align with safeguarding good practice, or the values that underpin our work, there is a chance it could undermine the whole initiative. Without dedicated capacity, it is not possible to undertake extensive due diligence or to ensure that organisations are not claiming affiliation with the initiative where there is none.

Balancing breadth of membership against ensuring organisations who join are genuinely committed to improving safeguarding, will remain an enduring issue.

SUBJECT MATTER

Safeguarding children in sport is something that everyone agrees is important – even if their organisation is struggling to make this a reality – and it is an area of alignment for many different organisations. This has meant that bringing together a group of organisations to work on this issue has been relatively easy.

That said, although everyone understands that children should be safe when they take part in sport, some of the terminology is more problematic when trying to create a shared understanding. 'Safeguarding' is an English term, well understood in some geographies, but unclear or unknown in many. It is also a term that is not easy to translate into other languages – which creates barriers to sharing learning and insights.

RESOURCES

A lack of financial resource has had both benefits and challenges. In terms of benefits, this challenging financial environment has led to a sense of 'we're all in it together' from the engaged members of the initiative - each providing insight and capacity for the benefit of the whole network. If one organisation was funded to drive this work forward, it could lead to others feeling less ownership or connection to the initiative.

In terms of the challenges, a lack of dedicated funding has hamstrung the initiative, meaning it is not able to have the impact as quickly or widely as members would like.

Activities like running a website, a mentoring programme, or a community of practice all require funding – as does producing resources, running an annual campaign, and making sure everything produced is available in several different languages – all of this work has been delivered on a shoestring, and is limited as a result.

CAPACITY

Everyone on the Advisory Board and Working Group engages in the initiative without any payment – either using time within their day jobs, or in their own free time. This means there are actually no dedicated staff for the initiative, and so capacity is always a challenge.

In addition, the Advisory Board and Working Group are mainly comprised of safeguarding experts and enthusiasts. This means that when we design a website, or a communication campaign, it is not clear we have the expertise within the members to develop something truly impactful.

DIVERSITY AND INCLUSION

The Advisory Board and Working Group are drawn from organisations from a range of continents including Africa, Asia, Europe, North America, Oceania, and South America. Meetings are held at different times over the course of the year, so that different time zones all have some meetings at convenient hours. The team has been proactive in connecting with organisations and individuals in different countries. Part of this has involved translating the International Safeguards into 12 different languages and delivering Safe Sport Day 2023 in three languages.

Whilst a diversity of organisations is represented on the Advisory Board and Working Group, the meetings of these groups are conducted in English without a translation option, and many of the representatives are from Europe even though they are based in different countries. This limits inclusion, reduces diversity of thought and representation, and limits the impact the initiative can have for children.

REPRESENTATION

In addition to efforts to become more geographically representative, the initiative has attempted to better engage the people we exist to serve – both those with lived experience of abuse and children in sport.

A survivor-led organisation sits on the Advisory Board – but there is the potential that this engagement is tokenistic and not truly meaningful.

Efforts to engage with children have been limited due to the resources required to be effective and the challenge of truly and ethically representing children from a range of sports, countries, and backgrounds. This inability to be truly representative has led to inaction, with member organisations leaning on their own youth voice mechanisms, and youth voice not playing a meaningful role outside of the initial research that created the International Safeguards.

Summary

In summary some of the main learning points we have identified to date are:

- **Be proactive in being inclusive** – both for those you exist to serve, and for different geographies. Recognise that this takes intentional action and some level of investment, (e.g. for translation and coordination) and budget for this. Make resources AND meetings available in a range of languages so you don't limit opportunities to participate, and work with those you exist to serve to explore how they would like to engage.
- **Balance shared ownership with ensuring you have the right level of resourcing.** Some constraints can be useful – they can help develop a shared sense of ownership and action – but ultimately, dedicated specialist staff are needed to maximise impact. Make sure you have the right level of resourcing, but also create decision-making structures that genuinely include members so that ownership is spread amongst all those that are involved, and not concentrated in the organisation holding the dedicated capacity or funding.
- **Coordination needs dedicated capacity** – networks don't just network – they need to be supported and coordinated. One of the reasons the International Safeguards initiatives has endured for more than 10 years is because there was an organisation taking on this coordination function from the outset. Without it, the network would have soon lost momentum and direction. But this takes time and therefore resource to do well, and should be factored in from the outset.

Questions

Some questions for the research community arising from this work are:

1. How to foster ownership amongst the members of a network or initiative? What combination of engagement and activity best promotes shared ownership and corresponding commitment?
2. How to be representative in the governance of international networks? What is some of the emerging good practice in terms of developing inclusive leadership groups that don't exclude some people from the structures of power and decision-making?

References/Further Information

Website: <https://safeinsport.org/>

8 Safeguards: <https://safeinsport.org/8-safeguards/>

Resources: <https://culture.safeinsport.org/resources>

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